

ISic3672

Small base reading SACR

Language

Latin

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe

Autopsy

2017-07-17

Last Change

2019-07-22 - Jonathan Prag edited the file based on autopsy in 2017

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

From material found in trenches L, LI and LX excavated by Carettoni in 1956, along the front of and within the west portico of the agora

Coordinates

37.997959, 14.262601

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa

Physical Description

A small limestone base, intact on all sides, chipped at the bottom of the front. Mouldings to top and bottom of left, front and right faces. The rear is roughly finished and plain, as is the underside. A large ovoid cavity occupies the rear two-thirds of the upper surface 12 cm x 8 cm , and c.1 cm deep

Dimensions

Height 6.6 cm

Width 17.6 cm

Depth 13.6 cm

Layout

A single line of latin letters occupies the field between the mouldings on the front face; the field is 3.4 cm high x 15.3 cm wide. There is a vacat before the text, and a recessed space after, the surface of the stone being lost.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Plain Latin capitals, with minimal serifs; S is fairly tall and shallow; A curves slightly towards the feet; C sits slightly above the line; R is closed, with curving tail.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 24-26 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation: n/a mm

Text

1. sacr(um)

Apparatus

Carettoni: SACR[-]

Translation (en)

Sacred

Commentary

Carettoni indicated one letter was missing at the end of the text, however the surface is lost and no traces are visible. Were there to be a letter (only A is realistically possible) the inscription would be very poorly aligned, whereas the abbreviation 'sacr(um)' produces a more centred text. The hole on the upper surface is likely to have held the base of a small statue which formed the dedication.

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 295 no.12a
fig.33

Facella, A. 2006. Alesa Arconidea: ricerche su un'antica città della Sicilia
tirrenica. Pisa. At 289

Prestianni Giallombardo, A. M. 2012. Spazio pubblico e memoria civica. Le
epigrafi dall'agora di Alesa. In Ampolo, C.(eds.), *Agora greca e agorai di Sicilia*.
Pisa. pp. 171-200. At 190 n.35

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-09-09): ISic3672. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI
edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4021601>

Photo J.Prag courtesy Soprintendenza BBCCAA di Messina